

Simulating the Effects of Climatic Changes on Tomato Using Regional Climate Model and DSSAT Crop Simulation Model

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Abstract

In order to fulfill requirements of people due to increase in population, all countries are developing new production strategies and plans for more efficient usage of the current resources. Climate change and agricultural drought are the most important environmental factors effecting agricultural production in the world. Aim of this study was determining the possible effects of climate changes on tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) production under created future climate conditions in the Mediterranean Region of Türkiye. For this purpose, 2 yr (2014-2015) field experiment was conducted for calibration and validation of Cropgro model of Decision Support System for Agrotechnology Transfer (DSSAT) version 4.5, Reference (1961-1990) and future (2001-2099) years climate data which were calibrated for Seyhan Basin of the International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP) Regional Climate Model system version 3 (RegCM3) were used to obtain future climate conditions by pseudo warming downscaling technique. According to the results that precipitation will decrease in a range of 21-25% also minimum and maximum temperatures will increase in a range of 16-29% in the both experiment years respectively. Cropgro of DSSAT model simulated that tomato yield will decrease about 16-17% while increase biomass in a range of 30-32% depending on the climate change effects in the future. It is recommended to compare the model outputs with obtained field datas in order for the model to make more appropriate estimations. DSSAT crop simulation models (CSM) can be used in agronomy studies to estimate yield and growth parameters.

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1. Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is the most produced fresh vegetable with 186.1 million tons of production in the world and Türkiye ranks third after India with 13.3 million tons of production (FAO, 2024). In 2023, tomatoes were produced on about 166.000 ha area in Türkiye and Mediterranean region provide 25.2% of total production in approximately 23.147 ha (TEPGE, 2024). Estimating crop yields in the future is becoming more important, especially considering the adverse effects of climatic changes. In this sense, as a result of studies on crop simulation models (CSM's), countries will be able to determine strategies for agricultural production policies for the future. Vegetable crops such as tomato and pepper are extremely sensitive to high temperatures during the reproductive phase. It is estimated that climate change in the agricultural sector will reduce global food production by 0.5% in the 2020s and by 2.3% in the 2050s. (Doğan et al., 2024). Increasing of average temperatures depending of climate change causes tomato production and effect adversely physiological stages of plant (Ayankojo and Morgan, 2020). In the present where climate change effects are felt, it is important to use more effective water sources for agricultural production and developing strategies in the future. Adverse effects of climate change will affect humans access to food and it is inevitable that this situation will cause changes on crop patterns. The reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and the deceleration of global climate change represent important environmental challenges that require the attention of all nations (Candemir et al., 2024a).

According to International Panel of Climate Change (IPCC) 6th assessment report, it was emphasized that temperature rising will continue by the end of 2050 (IPCC, 2023a). Especially in Mediterranean basin in Türkiye, it is estimated with climate models that temperatures will increase, agricultural droughts will be experienced and therefor water sources will be adversely effected

(Türkeş, 2020).

Continued greenhouse gas emissions will lead to increasing global warming, with the best estimate of reaching 1.5 °C in the near term in considered scenarios and modelled pathways. Every increment of global warming will intensify multiple and concurrent hazards (high confidence). Deep, rapid, and sustained reductions in greenhouse gas emissions would lead to a discernible slowdown in global warming within around two decades, and also to discernible changes in atmospheric composition within a few years (IPCC, 2023b).

According to RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios (IPCC, 2014) and regional climate models it is expected 1-6 °C increase in mean temperatures of Türkiye (Demircan et al., 2017). The biggest reason of global warming depends on climate change is increasing of greenhouse gas emissions by human effects (fossil fuel use, industrialization etc.) Other factors such as land use, agriculture and deforestation also affect climate variables and anthropogenic factors have big contributions (Yin et al., 2023). Among the gases which have greenhouse effects such as methane (CH₄), diazotmonoxide (N₂O), it is considered that the CO₂ concentration has the most impact on global warming as a result of human effects. Between 2021-2040 years temperature rise about 1.6 °C but this period will be earlier contributing by increase in CO₂ concentration. Under the high CO₂ scenarios earth surface average temperatures will be reached about 3.3-5.7 °C by the 2100 (Campbell-Lendrum et al., 2023). The use of technology in agriculture has led to improvements in agricultural production worldwide (Candemir et al., 2024b). Crop simulation models are widely use by all researchers that gives information about different crops under variable conditions (present and future). The Decision Support System for Agrotechnology Transfer (DSSAT) model (Jones et al., 2003) which was developed by International Benchmark Sites Network for Agrotechnology Transfer Project (IBSNAT) has Cropgro sub-model is a great tool that helps users such as to predicting climatic changes on crop, evaluating strategies

with limited water resources and determining performances of crops under different environmental conditions (Malik and Dechmi, 2019; Jiang et al., 2021; Feleke et al., 2021). The Crop simulation models (CSM's) use inputs for water deficit, different fertilization methods, etc., allow plant-based parameters to be simulated and different production strategies to be developed. Climate models are very important tools that guides researchers for predicting humidity, temperature, precipitation in the future and analyze temporal distribution and intensity of these parameters. In this sense, global and regional climate models are widely used in the world and have advantages and disadvantages in their own. Global climate models consider large areas while regional models provide high resolution informations.

Working with global (GCM) and regional climate (RCM) models have uncertainties that affects crop simulation model results and possible effects of climatic changes (Paudel and Hostikka, 2019). For this purpose, downscaling methods play important role to reduce these uncertainties and lead to improve success of the modeling in detailed basin level. Downscaling of RCMs is very important to have detailed information about climate change in basin. Considering the possible effects of climate changes in the future on region basis, detailed information provides more accurate desicions on agricultural production. Pseudo Global Warming Downscaling Method (PGWDS) is a technique that downscaling for a future climate using current weather data of a GCM added by the long-term mean difference between the present and the future climate projected by a GCM (Yoshikane et al., 2012).

Regional climate model (RCM) designed to suit the needs of the scientists by ICTP Earth System Physics (ESP) section (Pal et al., 2007). The version 3 of the ICTP RCM, named the ICTP Regional Climate Model 3 (RegCM3), is the third generation of a modeling framework originally described in Giorgi and Bates (1989); Dickinson et al. (1989); RegCMI, and later upgraded as described by Giorgi et al. (1993a,b); RegCM2

and Giorgi and Mearns (1999); RegCM2.5. RegCM3 is an integration of the main improvements that have been made to version 2.5 (RegCM2.5) as described in Giorgi and Mearns (1999). There are many studies confirm that crop simulation models (CSMs) can be used to predict the possible effects of climate changes on various crops such as rice (Alejo, 2021; Islam et al., 2021; Amnuaylojaroen et al., 2021), maize (Han et al., 2021; Araya et al., 2021), wheat (Yeşilköy and Şaylan, 2021; Harvey et al., 2021), sunflower (Gürkan et al., 2021; Deveci et al., 2019; Yeşilköy and Şaylan, 2021; Zhang et al., 2021), cotton (Lin, 2024; Baydar, 2010) tomato (Ventrella et al., 2012; Cammarano et al., 2020; Ayankojo and Morgan, 2020). In all studies it was obtained that CSMs are useful tools that giving information about crop yield and other phenologic stages of crops in the future. However, some climate change studies are available in Türkiye, evaluation of CSM's studies are limited and there is no study with tomato.

This study examined the possible effects of climatic changes in the future on tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) production with created future climate conditions of RegCM3 climate datas by using Pseudo Global Warming Downscaling method (PGWDS) and using Cropgro sub model of DSSAT CSM.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Experimental site and soil

Research was conducted in the experiment field of Alata Horticultural Research Institute Soil and Water Resources Location in Tarsus (36°55' W, 34°55' E, 50 m a.s.l.), Mersin-Türkiye, between 2014-2015 years. Some of climatic datas are given in Table 1 for the experiment years from the weather station of location field. Experiment field has typical East Mediterranean semi-arid climate. The maximum and average temperatures are 31.7-27.2 °C and 31.7-27.1 °C in July and total rainfall in experiment months are 182.3-111.3 mm respectively in the 2014-2015 experiment years.

Table 1. Monthly climatic datas of experiment field in 2014-2015 years

Years	Climatical parameters	Months				
		March	April	May	June	July
2014	Maximum temperatures, °C	21.2	24.5	26.5	29.5	31.7
	Minimum temperatures, °C	9.0	12.1	15.2	19.1	23.2
	Mean temperatures, °C	14.8	18.1	20.6	24.0	27.2
	Rainfall, mm	67.7	13.9	42.9	57.2	0.6
	Evaporation mm	100	134.5	160.7	185.8	201.9
	Relative humidity, %	63.1	64.4	70.0	70.4	73.2
2015	Maximum temperatures, °C	21.2	24.5	26.5	29.5	31.7
	Minimum temperatures, °C	9.0	12.1	15.2	19.1	23.2
	Mean temperatures, °C	14.0	15.5	21.2	23.9	27.1
	Rainfall, mm	70.2	8.0	30.4	1.3	1.4
	Evaporation, mm	83.9	110.0	158.8	177.7	202.1
	Relative humidity, %	63.3	62.7	65.3	70.5	71.5

Some of classified Arikli series experiment soil are given in Table 2. It was measured that pH ranged 7.91-8.08, electrical conductivity of soil (EC) 0.91-1.02 dS m⁻¹ and volumetric soil water content at field capacity and

permanent wilting point of the root-zone 29.6-30.7% and 12.7-19.7%, respectively. Mean bulk density varies from 1.30 to 1.42 g cm⁻³ while available water-holding capacity of the soil is 201 mm in the 60 cm soil depth.

Table 2. Some physical and chemical properties of experiment soil

Soil depth	Field capacity	Wilting point	Bulk density	Soil salinity	pH	CaCO ₃	Organic matter
cm	g g ⁻¹	g g ⁻¹	g cm ⁻³	dS m ⁻¹			%
0-30	30.70	19.75	1.30	0.914	7.91	21.78	1.80
30-60	29.97	19.12	1.40	0.976	7.97	28.30	1.06
60-90	29.64	12.71	1.42	1.028	8.08	24.80	0.77

2.2. Experimental design and irrigation treatment

‘Marmara F1’ tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) resistant to *Tomato yellow leaf curve virus* (TYLCV) and fusarium disease was used. Tomatoes were planted in a bed spacing of 120 cm with 50 cm row spacing on 1st and 2nd April respectively in the experiment years. There were five rows in each plot and the plot area was 96 m² with a length of 20 m and a width of 4.8 m. Tomato yield was determined by hand harvesting 10 m sections of center row in every plot in both years on 29 June. Harvest area was 12 m² in each plot.

Soil water content was followed by gravimetric method before irrigation applications for 1 week. Full irrigation treatment was considered for comparison of data observed from field experiment and

simulated data from crop growth model. Full irrigation was designed as water deficit in 60 cm root zone depth replenished to field capacity in 1 wk irrigation interval. The first irrigation treatment was applied when 70% flowering was seen in all plots by replenishing soil water in 60 cm profile to field capacity.

2.3. Agronomic practices and irrigation system

A total of 160 kg ha⁻¹ N, 50 kg ha⁻¹ P and 230 kg ha⁻¹ K fertilizers were applied as a recommended by Günay (2005). Fertilizers were applied as ammonium sulfate (NH₄)₂SO₄, monopotassium phosphate (MKP) and potassium nitrate (KNO₃). One-third of N and P were applied into the soil before planting. The remaining N, P, K and other minor elements were applied during irrigation season. All fertilizations were applied with injection pump method with drip irrigation

system so all plots received same uniformity and amount of total fertilizer.

Drip irrigation system was used in experiment. Laterals were applied on every row, drippers discharged 4 L h⁻¹ with pressure controlled and spaced at 40 cm. Well water was used as water source. The water taken from well with the deep well pump was transmitted

to the field by passing through 90 mm inlet and outlet diameters hydrocyclone and disk filters. Working pressure of the system was applied 200 kPa in the inlet of the filters.

2.4. Measurements and observations

The amount of irrigation water was calculated using the following Equation 1. (Gönen et al., 2024).

$$I = A \times P \times \Delta S \quad (1)$$

where I is the applied irrigation amount (L), P is the percentage of wetted area and ΔS is water deficit in 60 cm soil profile (mm). Wetted area was followed as cover percentage by ratio of cover width to row spacing and taken constant when reached 70%. Plant height (cm), biomass (kg ha⁻¹), leaf area index (cm² cm⁻²) and yield (kg ha⁻¹) parameters were followed during growing season of tomato for calibration and validation of the model. The DSSAT model version 4.5 was calibrated by comparing mentioned parameters with simulated by model and observed data from field experiment with crop genetic coefficients. The t-test was applied in order to determine the differences between simulated by model and observed from field experiment datas at 5% of significant level (Steel and Torrie, 1980).

2.5. Downscaled RegCM3 RCM by pseudo-global-warming method and DSSAT Cropgro CSM

In the study, future climate conditions obtained with usage of Theoretical Physics (ICTP) Regional Climate Model system version 3 (RegCM3) with the help of the pseudo-warming downscaling technique. There are some positive and negative aspects that the PWG method presents to researchers. The term “Pseudo Global Warming” (PGW) refers to a simulation strategy in regional climate modeling. The strategy consists of directly imposing large-scale changes in the climate system on a control regional climate simulation (usually representing current conditions) by modifying the boundary

conditions. This differs from the traditional dynamic downscaling technique where output from a global climate model (GCM) is used to drive regional climate models (RCMs). The Pseudo Global Warming method (PGW) approach makes climate projections with a comparatively short simulation duration possible also reduce the computational and storage costs of climate projections if a reanalysis-driven evaluation simulation is pre-existing. On the other hand, using the same synoptic forcing in PGW implies that potential changes in intra-annual and interannual variability might be missed in the PGW approach also preparing PGW simulations needs manual work to produce the initial and lateral boundary conditions (Brogli et al., 2023).

In the study long-term mean differences between present and future climate data of regional climate model (RCM) added to current weather data to create downscaled future climate conditions. For this purpose, The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye funded “Climate Change Scenarios for Turkey” Project (Dalfes et al. 2008) which was conducted at the Istanbul Technical University in conjunction with the General Directorate of Meteorology Service between 2006-2008 years, reference (1961-1990) and future (2001-2099) climate monthly mean data of Regional Climate Model version 3 (RegCM3) including minimum and maximum temperatures, precipitations and net radiation which were calibrated for Seyhan

basin were used. Differences between reference and future data were added to 2014-2015 experiment years climate data of the study. In this way future climate conditions were created with accepted 700 ppm CO₂ concentration.

Cropgro submodel of the DSSAT crop simulation model was run with required minimum data sets including minimum and maximum temperatures, net radiation and precipitation. These climatic data were taken from meteorological station of experiment site. Calculated amounts of irrigation water, fertilization applications, physical and chemical properties of soil data which were taken from experiment were entered in the model for run. Validation of model was done by accepting crop genetic coefficients without differences between simulated and observed data at 5 % significant level. Possible effects of

climatic changes on tomato in the future was determined by running DSSAT model again with created climate scenario and determined crop genetic coefficients in the two experiment years (2014-2015).

3. Results and Discussion

Crop genetic coefficients were obtained with comparison of observed and simulated values explained before. Results of applied t-test at 5% significant level between observed data from field and simulated data from model were given in Tables 3 and 4 for experiment years. There were nonsignificant differences between observed and simulated plant height (cm), biomass (kg ha⁻¹) and yield (kg ha⁻¹) values at 5% level. However, observed and simulated leaf area index (LAI) values were significant (P<0.05) in both experimental years.

Table 3. T-test results related to observed from field and simulated from model (2014)

Parameters	Observed		Simulated		P
	Mean value	Variance	Mean value	Variance	
Plant height, cm	62.5	285.66	61.5	232.6	0.51
Biomass, kg ha ⁻¹	4620.5	4579864	4750.0	4981281	0.09
Leaf area index, cm ² cm ⁻²	3.23	0.006	2.49	0.12	0.04
Yield, kg ha ⁻¹	4768.6	355984	4102.7	4771459	0.20

P< 0.05: significant

Table 4. T-test results related to observed from field and simulated from model (2015)

Parameters	Observed		Simulated		P
	Mean value	Variance	Mean value	Variance	
Plant height, cm	76.5	128.33	74.2	144.91	0.09
Biomass, kg ha ⁻¹	7260.7	3378588	7630.7	4436354	0.21
Leaf area index, cm ² cm ⁻²	3.72	0.751	3.50	0.830	0.01
Yield, kg ha ⁻¹	4166.80	40524.33	4066.22	47922.33	0.79

P< 0.05: significant

Crop genetic coefficients were determined with this method according to tomato cultivar on study for calibration version 4.5 of DSSAT model. It is not possible to make a separate calibration for LAI values. Therefore, plant height (cm), biomass (kg ha⁻¹) and yield (kg ha⁻¹) values were taken into consideration during the calibration of the model. At the beginning of the experiments (2014-2015) all plots received 82.9-60.0 mm of irrigation water in

order to establish good plant standing in field in the experiments also 397.9-409.0 mm of irrigation water applied with drip irrigation system in the experimental years respectively. The DSSAT model was made ready to run for the future conditions after calibration and validation stages. In order to obtain future climate data as mentioned before PGWDS technique results were used. Calculated temperature data for the reference and future

years and their differences are given in Table 5 for 2014-2015.

Table 5. RegCM3 1961-1990 and 2001-2099 years mean temperatures and differences (2014-2015)

Months	RegCM3 mean temperature value (2001-2099)	RegCM3 mean temperature value (1961-1990)	RegCM3 mean temperature differences 2001-2099 and 1961-1990
	(°C)	(°C)	(°C)
January	5.44	1.98	3.46
February	6.70	3.71	2.99
March	9.98	6.56	3.42
April	13.84	10.69	3.15
May	20.35	15.59	4.76
June	24.40	20.30	4.10
July	26.90	22.19	4.71
August	26.70	21.28	5.42
September	23.07	17.88	5.19
October	16.96	12.59	4.37
November	10.07	7.10	2.97
December	6.20	3.12	3.08

According to PGWDS results, the highest calculated temperature between 2001-2099 years was 26.90 °C in July and 22.19 °C in July between 1961-1990. Calculated maximum temperature differences between mentioned

years was 5.42 °C in August. Precipitation data for the reference and future years also their differences are given in Table 6. for 2014-2015 experiment years.

Table 6. RegCM3 1961-1990 and 2001-2099 years mean precipitations and differences (2014-2015)

Months	RegCM3 mean precipitation value (2001-2099)	RegCM3 mean precipitation value (1961-1990)	RegCM3 mean precipitation differences 2001- 2099 and 1961-1990
	mm	mm	mm
January	3.00	3.95	-0.95
February	2.81	3.21	-0.40
March	2.94	2.55	0.39
April	1.86	2.49	-0.63
May	0.69	1.59	-0.90
June	0.17	0.37	-0.20
July	0.06	0.10	-0.04
August	0.10	0.19	-0.09
September	0.13	0.35	-0.22
October	1.41	1.20	0.21
November	2.77	2.93	-0.16
December	3.16	3.28	-0.12

Highest precipitation differences in the future years (2001-2099) was calculated as 3.16 mm in December while 3.95 mm in the reference years (1961-1990) in January. Calculated maximum precipitation differences between future (2001-2099) and reference (1961-1990) years was 0.95 mm decrease in

January. Based on three GCMs and two RCPs total precipitation would decrease by 18.1-21.2% for Konya province in Türkiye (Gürkan et al., 2021). It was determined that higher temperatures and decreases in precipitations were obtained for the future in both years of the study. Demircan et al. (2017) reported that

according to IPCC reports temperatures will raise in Türkiye by using RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios by 1.5-2.5 and 2.5-3.6 °C respectively at the end of this century. Yıldırım et al. (2021) determined that temperatures will increase about 1.35, 2.13 and 4.11 °C for three future periods 2021-2040, 2046-2065 and 2081-2100, reflecting the beginning, middle and end of the century, respectively in Alata River Basin in the Mediterranean Region. Future years' climate conditions

(precipitations, maximum and minimum temperatures) were determined by adding calculated differences mentioned above on to the climate data which were taken from field meteorology station in the first experiment year (2014) (Tables 7 and 8). It was obtained that mean minimum and maximum temperatures will increase about 29-16% (from 25.1 to 29.1 °C) respectively and precipitation will decrease 21% (from 1.1 to 0.8 mm) in the future for the 2014.

Table 7. RegCM3 Calculated mean maximum and minimum temperatures for the future (2014)

Months	RegCM3 mean temperature (°C) differences 2001- 2099 and 1961- 1990	2014 experiment year mean maximum temperatures	Future years mean maximum temperatures	2014 experiment year mean minimum temperatures	Future years mean minimum temperatures
		°C	°C	°C	°C
January	3.46	17.72	21.18	5.84	9.30
February	2.99	18.99	21.98	5.71	8.70
March	3.42	21.23	24.65	8.99	12.41
April	3.15	24.47	27.62	12.09	15.24
May	4.76	26.51	31.27	15.12	19.88
June	4.10	29.49	33.59	19.02	23.12
July	4.71	31.66	36.37	23.15	27.86
August	5.42	33.44	38.86	23.54	28.96
September	5.19	31.32	36.51	20.28	25.47
October	4.37	27.64	32.01	16.48	20.85
November	2.97	21.19	24.16	7.34	10.31
December	3.08	17.63	20.71	3.14	6.22
	Mean	25.10	29.07	13.39	17.36

Table 8. RegCM3 precipitations for the future (2014)

Months	RegCM3 Mean precipitations differences 2001-2099 and 1961-1990	2014 experiment year mean precipitations	Future years mean precipitations
	mm	mm	mm
January	-0.95	3.1	2.15
February	-0.40	0.8	0.4
March	0.39	2.3	2.69
April	-0.64	0.5	-0.14
May	-0.90	1.4	0.5
June	-0.20	1.9	1.7
July	-0.04	0.0	-0.04
August	-0.09	0.2	0.11
September	-0.21	0.0	-0.21
October	0.21	1.5	1.71
November	-0.16	0.5	0.34
December	-0.11	0.1	-0.1
	Mean	1.02	0.8

In the 2015 second year of the study, future climate conditions were obtained by using results of PGWDS temperatures and precipitations differences which were determined (Tables 5 and 6) before were added 2015-year climate data from meteorology station in the field (Tables 9 and 10).

According to the 2015 second year of the research, it was obtained that mean minimum and maximum temperatures will increase about 19-16% (from 24.7 to 28.7 °C) respectively, and precipitation will decrease 25 % (from 0.1 to 0.01 mm) in the future for 2015.

Table 9. RegCM3 Calculated mean maximum and minimum temperatures for the future (2015)

Months	RegCM3 mean temperature differences 2001- 2099 and 1961- 1990	2015 experiment year mean maximum temperatures	Future years mean maximum temperatures	2015 experiment year mean minimum temperatures	Future years mean minimum temperatures
	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C
January	3.46	14.58	18.04	7.43	10.89
February	2.99	15.75	18.74	8.65	11.64
March	3.42	20.03	23.45	11.65	15.07
April	3.15	21.43	24.58	13.87	17.02
May	4.76	26.39	31.15	19.29	24.05
June	4.10	29.18	33.28	19.02	13.12
July	4.71	32.28	36.99	25.87	30.58
August	5.42	34.35	39.77	27.17	32.59
September	5.19	32.88	38.07	20.28	25.47
October	4.37	28.46	32.83	25.26	29.63
November	2.97	23.67	26.64	14.22	17.19
December	3.08	17.63	20.71	3.14	6.22
	Mean	24.72	28.69	16.32	19.46

Table 10. RegCM3 precipitations for the future (2015)

Months	RegCM3 Mean precipitations differences 2001-2099 and 1961-1990	2015 experiment year mean precipitations	Future years mean precipitations
	mm	mm	mm
January	-0.95	3.1	2.15
February	-0.40	0.8	0.40
March	0.39	2.3	2.69
April	-0.64	0.5	-0.14
May	-0.90	1.4	0.50
June	-0.20	1.9	1.70
July	-0.04	0.0	-0.04
August	-0.09	0.2	0.11
September	-0.21	0.0	-0.21
October	0.21	1.5	1.71
November	-0.16	0.5	0.34
December	-0.11	0.1	-0.01
	Mean	1.03	0.77

In addition to all this progress including determination of future climate conditions and calibration and validation of DSSAT model mentioned before, the response of tomato plant to climate changes was predicted by re-run of the DSSAT model where as CO₂ concentration was assumed to be 700 ppm in model. It was simulated by DSSAT model that tomato yield will be 3391 kg ha⁻¹ with decrease about 17% and 3464 kg ha⁻¹ with decrease about 16% respectively depending on climate changes in the future in both experiment years. Increasing in air temperature and changes in rainfall caused shortening tomato phenology and 15% reduction in yield (Cammarano et al., 2020).

Ventrella et al. (2012) reported that Cropgro model simulated reduction in tomato yield for the future climate conditions and production levels were reduced. Cropgro tomato of DSSAT model simulated that when temperatures were 10-20% warmer caused decrease on tomato yield 52% to 85% according to present days in the future (Ayankojo and Morgan, 2020). Lee et al. (2011) reported that under A2 (medium-high) climate change scenarios tomato yield decreased 9%. Simulated with model for the future and observed from field experiment tomato yields are given in Table 11.

Table 11. Tomato yields in present and future years (2014-2015)

Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	2014		2015	
	Present	Future	Present	Future
	4103	3391	4116	3464

Biomass values simulated with model and observed from field experiment are given in Figures 1a and 1b in the 2014-2015 experiment years. It was determined that mean biomass

values will be 5530 kg ha⁻¹ with increase about 30% and 8858 kg ha⁻¹ with increase about 22 % in the future respectively in both experiment years.

Figure 1a. Simulated biomass values related to future with Cropgro of CSM-DSSAT (2014)

Figure 1b. Simulated biomass values related to future with Cropgro of CSM-DSSAT (2015)

Due to changes in climate change tomato biomass accumulation and leaf area index increased with increase in temperatures (Ayankojo and Morgan, 2020). Simulated and observed plant height values are given in Figures 2a and 2b in both experimental years.

The DSSAT crop simulation model simulated that plant height will be 48.5 cm with decrease about 22% and 59.0 cm with decrease about 23% in the future comparing to present years in the experiment years respectively.

Figure 2a. Simulated plant height values 2014 (a) related to future with Cropgro of CSM-DSSAT (2014).

Figure 2b. Simulated plant height values 2015 (b) related to future with Cropgro of CSM-DSSAT (2014).

4. Conclusion

This study was carried out to determine possible effects of climate change in the future on tomato with using crop simulation model (DSSAT) and regional climate model (RegCM3). The validation and calibration stages of crop growth models with observed datas from field and simulated by models are inevitable for the success of the models. In this study observed and simulated datas were statistically compared and made available for Seyhan Basin. Using RegCM3 regional climate model data, it has been determined that there will be a decrease of 16-29% in temperatures and 21-25% in precipitation depending on climate change in the future. Considering the determined climate datas, it has been predicted that there will be a decrease of 16-17% in the yield of tomato, increase of 30-32% in biomass values and a decrease of 22-23% in plant height.

The DSSAT crop simulation model can predict not only crop growth stages but also parameters such as soil water consumption and evapotranspiration. Accuracy and availability of climate datas are important in the estimation of these parameters. Studies on parameters mentioned above are increasing day by day and evaluations are made on the positive and negative aspects of the models.

In the study, the DSSAT model could not estimate the LAI values obtained from the field experiment, while it gave positive responses in other parameters like plant height, yield and

biomass parameters at the calibration stage. The development of the DSSAT model is in progress and aims to provide researchers with more consistent results in the calibration of crop genetic coefficients. On the other hand, more researches should be done on the statistical comparison of the model estimations with the data obtained from the field.

Nowadays, there are different climate scenarios for determining the effects of climatic changes. Each scenario makes inferences about the future in different ranges and with optimistic and pessimistic approaches. In particular, examining climatic changes on a regional and downscaled will represent more significant results.

According to the results of this study, it was concluded that climatic changes will create adverse effects in agricultural production in Seyhan Basin in the future and there will be a decrease in tomato yield. In this sense, it is necessary to determine the strategies in agricultural production by selecting drought resistant varieties, using water resources more effectively and making yield prediction studies for the future. Also breeding studies on tomato varieties that are more resistant to the adverse effects of climate change and related drought in the future is important. The development of resistant varieties is the most important method for unfavorable conditions. In this sense, better protection of gene resources and breeding studies should be more widespread. It is determined that DSSAT (CSM) crop

simulation model is useful and successful tools to predict climatic changes on agricultural production if calibration and validation stages are done correctly.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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